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22

Analysing Stress Management Among Higher Secondary School Students Of Aurangabad City, With Respect To Gender

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Abstract

“Outer Circumstances and events don’t create stress. It is our response to them which creates stress.” Nuemberger Phil (1990). Stress is a fact of life and individuals react to stress in different ways. Some individuals deal with stressors in a positive way with a proper understanding of the phenomenon and its effect. Taking appropriate action to optimise, reduce or prevent stress may be beneficial for the individual. Stress management is a means to enhance coping with external stressors and their internal consequences. The present study was conducted to study the overall stress management level and also to compare the stress management level with respect to gender among the junior college students. A sample of 100 junior college science students was selected from Aurangabad district by random sampling technique. The data was collected by the stress management scale designed and standardized by Dr.Namrata arora and Dr.Vandana Kaushik. The results revealed that the overall stress management level among the students is moderate and there was a significant difference observed in the stress management level of the male and female science students.

Keywords: Stress Management, Gender, Transformational coping, Regressive approach

Introduction

As cited in (MALLACH, 1996), Stress is a major 20th-century ailment, producing an increase in blood sugar level, adrenalin, heart rate, cholesterol level and blood pressure. Heart attacks and strokes now kill more people than all other diseases combined. Stress is a fact of life and individuals react to stress in different ways. Some individuals deal with stressors in a positive way with a proper understanding of the phenomenon and its effect. Taking appropriate action to optimise, reduce or prevent stress may be beneficial for the individual. Stress management is a means to enhance coping with external stressors and their internal consequences. As prevention is better than cure, steps should be taken to prevent the occurrence of stress rather than treat its harmful effects or bear a heavy cost when the damage is already done. Stress can be reduced by exercise, yoga, music and interventions. As cited in (Gentry, Chung, Aung, & Keller, 2007), Stress protects humans from danger as it is a natural physiological mechanism present in the human body. As observed in the (National Institutes of Health [NIH], 2007), When stress occurs, the human body prepares

for quick action by releasing hormones that increase alertness and focus, but if the source of stress does not disappear, stress hormones can persist in the body. A wide range of physical and psychological illnesses, such as obesity, gastrointestinal disorders, cardiovascular disorders, skin disorders, anxiety attacks, and depression has been linked to, continual exposure to stress hormones.

Approaches of Coping with Stress

1) Passive approach: When people either suffer or deny the experienced stress or put the blame on others it is called passive approach. It is the reactive strategy or dysfunctional style of coping.

2) Active approach: It occurs when people face the experienced realities of stress and clarify the problems through negotiations and discussions with other members. This is proactive strategy or functional style of coping. The active approaches are more approved by Social Scientists as they are supposed to be more effective and healthy when compared to passive approaches or dysfunctional styles (Pareek, 1983).

Stress Coping Strategies

Various investigators have pursued two different approaches to the study of coping. On one hand some researchers have emphasized general coping traits, styles or dispositions (Goldstein, 1973), while on the other hand (Cohen and Lazarus, 1973) have preferred to study the active on-going strategies in a particular stress situation.

Maddi & Kobasa (1984) talked about two forms of coping- Transformational and Regressive.

1) Transformational coping involves altering the events so that they are less stressful. This can be done through interaction with events, optimistic thinking and acting towards them decisively and change them in a less stressful direction.

2) Regressive approach includes a strategy where one thinks about the events pessimistically and acts evasively to avoid contact with them.

Lazarus (1975) suggested a classification of coping processes which emphasizes two major categories: direct actions and palliative modes namely direct action coping and palliative coping. Social and emotional support available to the person helps him / her to effectively cope with stress. In their study (Gentry et al., 2007), observed that, interventions helps people to cope better with stress. Interventions for women may focus on increasing the use of adaptive strategies such as praying and talking to friends and family, while interventions for men may introduce the use of adaptive coping strategies such as exercise and actively fighting causes of stress. They have also observed that gender differences in stress levels and coping in Hawaii are similar to previous studies conducted on the mainland. As cited in (Gentry et al., 2007), it has been observed the importance of gender's influence on stress and have consistently revealed that women report higher levels of chronic and daily stressors than men.

In his dissertation, (MALLACH, 1996), has observed that the male and female professionals differ significantly in only two of the six coping mechanisms measured, namely social support and symptom management; that men and women do not differ significantly in terms of coping repertoire; and that women cope more effectively than their male counterparts with work-related stress.

Review of related literature and research

Shannon and Elizabeth (2008), investigated the relationships among stress, coping, and mental health in 139 students participating in an International Baccalaureate (IB) high school diploma program. Results showed that students in an IB program perceived significantly more stress than a sample of 168 of their general education peers.

Joyce Walker, Extension Center for Youth Development(2005),

Adolescence Stress and Depression, Adults commonly tell young people that the teenage years are the "best years of your life." The rosy remembrance highlights happy groups of high school students energetically involved at a dance or sporting event, or sipping sodas at a local restaurant. This is only part of the picture. Life for many young people is a painful tug of war filled with mixed messages and conflicting demands from parents, teachers, coaches, employers, friends and oneself. Growing up—negotiating a path between independence and reliance on others—is a tough business. It creates stress, and it can create serious depression for young people ill-equipped to cope, communicate and solve problems. Teenagers, like adults, may experience stress every day and can benefit from learning stress management skills. Most teens experience more stress when they perceive a situation as dangerous, difficult, or painful and they do not have the resources to cope.

Analysis and Interpretation of the Results

Table no.1: Table showing the overall stress management level in the students:

Aspect	Obtained mean	Range	Interpretation
Overall Stress management level	108.83	105-120	Moderate Stress management level.

From Table no.1, we can observe that the obtained mean for overall stress management level in the students is 108.83 which falls in the range of moderate level. Hence we can say that the stress management level in the higher secondary science students (Junior College) is moderate.

Table no.2: Table showing stress management level in the students with respect to gender:

Sr. No.	Gender	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Sig. at 0.05 level	Interpretation
1.	Male	104.86	27.66	3.688	1.96	Significant
2.	Female	112.13	22.72			
df=98						

From Table no.2, the obtained Mean for the stress management of males was 140.133 and S.D was 26.066. The obtained Mean for the stress management of females was 112.13 and S.D was 22.72. The obtained t-value was 3.688 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it can be interpreted that there is a significant difference between the stress management of males and females studying at the higher secondary stage. Females possess more stress management than male higher secondary science students (Junior College) of Aurangabad District.

Conclusion

The results and interpretation obtained from this research suggests that, the stress management level of the higher secondary science students (Junior College) is moderate. As per the results obtained it has been observed that the, females students possess more stress management than male students of higher secondary science students (Junior College) of Aurangabad District.

Graph showing the Comparison of mean scores on level of Stress Management Levels with respect to Gender

Suggestions

The Coping Mechanisms for Stress Management in Adolescents:

- Adolescents must learn to solve problems.
- Should develop positive relationships at home, school, with peers and adults.
- Adolescents should have Clear Goals.
- Adolescents should have Permission and ability to learn from mistakes.
- Adolescents should develop competencies (academic, social, life skills).

- Adolescents being Consistent, Positive and disciplined helps in combating stress.
- Adolescents should take good nutritional food and exercise regularly.
- Adolescents should take time out to relax or to do recreational activities.
- Adolescents should develop hobbies.

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